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D2: Report on the technical specifications and the communication workflow for sensor-equipped smart medical implants within an MRI scanner

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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Glossary

MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
RF	Radiofrequency
SAR	Specific Absorption Rate
DBS	Deep Brain Stimulator
pTx	Parallel Transmission
IPG	Implantable Pulse Generator
AIMD	Active Implantable Medical Device
IIU	Implant Interface Unit
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
SoC	System on Chip
CP	Circular Polarization
OP	Orthogonal Projection
WC	Worst Case
ADC	Analog to Digital Converter
RMS	Root Mean Square
RAM	Random Access Memory
FMEA	Failure Modes and Effects Analysis
RPN	Risk Priority Number

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1 Summary

Medical implants pose a safety risk for patients in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) due to radiofrequency induced tissue heating. Current safety practices rely on simulations covering a large variety of exposure scenarios leading to overly conservative RF power limits that reduce image quality and impose a high burden on the clinics. A smart medical implant safety concept can be used for personalized safety assessments and on-the-fly monitoring of RF-induced heating, substantially improving current clinical practice. In this report the technical specifications, methodology, communication workflow and risk assessment of the proposed safety concept are introduced. Proof-of-concept results have been published in peer-reviewed publications.¹⁻⁴

2 Introduction

MRI scanners emit time-varying radiofrequency (RF) pulses to image the target tissue. The strength and frequency of the applied RF power typically varies at hundreds of watts within a frequency range of typically 64-298MHz, depending on the static magnetic field strength of the MR system. In order to prevent excessive RF energy being absorbed in tissue, defined as the specific absorption rate (SAR), the time-averaged RF power is limited by international standards typically to 2 W/kg for whole body RF coil excitation and 3.2 W/kg for head only RF exposures.⁵

When an MR scan is conducted on a patient with an active implantable medical device (AIMD), such as a deep brain stimulator (DBS), the interaction of the RF excitation coil of the MR system with the electrically conductive wires and electrodes of the AIMD can cause substantial increases in RF-induced local SAR and respective tissue heating around the implanted electrodes.^{6,7} The induced local SAR is patient-, implant-, MR- and exam-specific leading to complex simulation models and high uncertainties in the RF safety assessment applied in current standards⁸ to prevent potential tissue damage, e.g. in the brain.⁹ As a consequence SAR limits are substantially reduced in the presence of AIMDs, e.g., from 3.2 W/kg head SAR without implant to only 0.1 W/Kg with an implant present.¹⁰ These limitations affect the imaging, thus, diagnostic performance of the MRI system.

Another challenge in the currently implemented implant safety routine in hospitals, is that the sole responsibility rests with the clinical personnel. Integrating implants into MRI workflows imposes substantial organizational challenges and costs on a hospital.^{11,12} MRI scans are often significantly delayed or even denied.^{13,14}

3 Smart implant safety concepts

The smart medical implant safety concept is based on personalized measurements rather than generalized simulations.¹⁻⁴

Small and inexpensive physical sensors can be attached to the implant electrodes², embedded in the implant casing³ or even unmodified commercial components, such as shown for DBS implants^{15,16}, can be used to assess the momentary and patient-specific RF hazard. If this information is transmitted to the operator or MR scanner, the RF exposure can be controlled to safe but not overly conservative RF power levels. If the MR system and RF coil support more than one independent RF transmission channel, i.e. so-called multi-channel transmission or parallel transmission (pTx), the sensed implant information can be intelligently utilized to substantially mitigate the RF-induced heating without the need to reduce the transmitted RF power and compromise image quality.^{2-4,17}

The components needed for establishing this novel safety concept are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2. Two approaches are feasible, a manual approach, which involves the MR operator to monitor potential unsafe conditions and who sets safe RF power limitations on the MR scanner. This approach is limited in performance but has the big advantage that it can be implemented by the AIMD manufacturers alone, it works with all MRI scanners without modification and thus can enter the market very quickly. The second is an automated approach, where the implant communicates directly with the MR system for implant safe scanning. This approach requires the implant and MRI manufacturers to agree on a standardized communication protocol but it is ultimately the more performant mode.

In the following chapters the requirements for each component are described including a risk analysis.

Figure 1 Components of the manual smart medical implant safety concept, where an operator reads and sets implant safe MR scanning values.

Figure 2 Components of the automatic smart medical implant safety concept, where the implant communicates with the MRI scanner.

3.1 Manual control by an MR Operator

In the manual monitoring mode, the AIMD communicates wirelessly with an implant interface unit (IIU). The MR operator starts the calibration sequence on the IIU and on the MR scanner. After the implant measures the RF-induced implant heating through the integrated sensor, this information is being transmitted wirelessly from the implantable pulse generator (IPG) to the IIU, which postprocesses and displays the results. These values can be directly translated into safe RF power limits by the operator and set at the MR scanner for an implant safe scanning mode in either single channel or multichannel transmission mode. During the actual MR scan in implant safe mode, the IIU monitors the sensor values from the implant continuously and can give an alarm in case of unforeseen events during the scan, e.g. a patient movement leading to excessive implant heating.

The MR operator sees the quantitative hazard information on the display and can react accordingly, e.g. abort the scan and adjust the new RF transmission settings after another calibration scan.

3.2 Automatic control and communication between implant and MRI scanner

In the automatic monitoring mode, the IIU communicates directly with both the implant and the MRI scanner. The IIU triggers a calibration scan on the MR scanner, collects the implant measurement data from the implant sensor during that scan and computes safe scan parameters from this data. These parameters are then transferred directly to the MR scanner to set the implant safe mode. The MR Operator interacts only with the MRI scanner's user interface (UI). The UI indicates that smart implant scanning is feasible, and the operator performs all the normal workflow tasks. Monitoring of RF-induced heating, adjustments of the RF power and abortion of an MR scan are performed by the MR system. In principle the IIU could be part of the implant, part of the MR scanner or an independent unit as displayed in Figure 2. An independent unit has the advantage of easier standardization, since the communication between IIU and implant is independent from the communication between IIU and MR scanner. This facilitates the implementation of independent communication workflows, which otherwise would require extensive negotiations and agreements between MR and implant manufacturers. For both safety concepts a robust communication workflow needs to be established that includes the type of data that needs to be transmitted, the timing requirements for data transmission and consistency checks.

4 Technical requirements

In the following the different requirements for the individual modules (AIMD, IIU, MR Scanner) are explained and summarized.

4.1 Implant hardware and sensor calibration

An implant is considered smart in the above-mentioned context if it fulfils the following requirements:

1. A **sensor** that measures changes of a suitable hazard metric, e.g. E-fields, induced RF currents, or temperatures at the implant electrodes. The sensor can be an external sensor such as a diode or thermistor² or the electrode itself.^{2,3,15,16}

2. An **electrical readout circuit** that digitizes the sensor information, typically located in the implants IPG.
3. A **wireless communication module**, typically located in the implants IPG. All modern AIMDs have such a module already included in their IPGs.

An example open-source reference¹⁸ implant that was constructed for proof-of-concept measurements is depicted in Figure 3 with the electrical readout circuit and wireless communication module illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 3 Example reference implant used for proof-of-concept implant safety studies.³

Figure 4: The schematic of the reference implant electronics containing readout system, processing unit and wireless communication system for E-field sensing. The receive switch protects the electronics from high RF pulses during normal MR operation mode and switches to measurement mode for sensor readouts. The Schottky rectifier measures the root-mean-squared E-field detected from the electrode and the Bluetooth Low Energy module is for wireless communication. The electronics of the wireless communication module are protected by an additional filter.³

The readout circuit of the reference implant consists of a Schottky barrier diode (D2) rectifier module with an RLC filter (R2, L3, C4), which was embedded in the IPG and connected to the 12-bit ADC module of a BLE v5.2 system-on-chip (SoC). The average E-field power due to RF-induced currents dissipated at the implant electrode is read by a Schottky barrier diode (D2) rectifier module with an RLC filter (R2, L3, C4) was embedded in the implant casing and connected to the 12-bit ADC module of the SoC. In addition, an RF switch module was implemented based on a PIN diode (D1). D1 is biased and controlled by the SoC via the digitally adjustable resistance R1 and enables sensor signal measurements to assess implant heating while simultaneously protecting the ADC. L1 serves as an RF choke to attenuate RF-induced voltages at the digital port, protecting the port from high peak power RF pulses during MR measurements other than safety related measurements. L2 is used as

the DC return path for the PIN diode bias, and C1 and C3 are used to block unwanted DC currents. The electronics circuit was enclosed within a metallic box acting as a Faraday cage with a 2.4 GHz Bluetooth antenna located outside. The antenna was connected through a high-pass filter adjusted to pass the Bluetooth signal, while blocking MR frequencies, to protect the SoC. More details can be found in the publication.³ The implant was published as open-source hardware for easy rebuild, modification and testing: <https://www.opensourceimaging.org/project/wireless-reference-implant/>.

Implant sensors and calibration

Different types of sensors can be utilized to detect hazardous RF-induced heating. With respect to the presented reference implant example, root-mean-square sensors relax the sampling rate requirements for the ADC to kHz instead of a several hundred MHz to GHz when using time-domain sensors. Every sensor requires calibrations to transfer the transmitted digitized values into a physically present E-field, current or temperature in tissue. The calibration typically includes the electronic circuit such as the imperfections of the Schottky rectifier and the protective RF switch circuit in the reference implant example from Figure 4. Circuit simulations, such as in Figure 5 can be carried out to address losses, nonlinearities and settling times for different sampling rates (Figure 6). Please note that these calibrations can in principle be frequency dependent, so a device calibration might need to be repeated for different MR field strengths (e.g. $B_0 = 1.5$ T or 3 T) and corresponding excitation frequencies (e.g. ^1H , ^{23}Na).

Figure 5 Offline circuit calibration simulation for the implant hardware. Here, the small nonlinearity of the Schottky diode (D2) and the conduction losses of the RF switch (D1) and D2 are investigated in order to improve the accuracy of the measured sensor signal.

Figure 6: Simulation result depicting settling times for the implant under test. For 0.5-4.0 V input signal amplitude, the settling time can be chosen >1.2 μs to accurately sample an induced E-field signal.

In the example in Figure 6, an ADC sampling time of about 7.5 μs was chosen to be well above the saturation point at about 1.2 μs. After ADC adjustments, the linearity and lower/upper limits of the sensor readout needs to be determined. The relationship of the input signal at the IPG input and the sensor signal at the ADC are shown in Figure 7. Accuracies to predict the correct input signal based on the sensor measurements at very low amplitudes (<0.15 V) are very low. Similarly, above 4.3 V the maximum absolute limits of the utilized ADC electronics are reached, which needs to be considered.

Figure 7: Exemplified relationship between the RF-induced voltage at the input of the readout circuitry and the output of the rectified signal at the output of the Schottky diode (sensor signal measured at ADC). For very low RF-induced signals the accuracy to reconstruct the input signal from the sensor measurements is low. The upper boundary of about ~4.3 V also refers to the maximum voltage range for the investigated ADC unit.

After reliably detecting uncertainties and a specified range for the sensor readings, the sensor signals need to be calibrated against the actual E-field, current or temperature measurements.⁴ For this part, the implant manufacturer can refer to existing safety standards and their corresponding measurement and/or simulation procedures.^{8,19}

In Figure 8, a non-standardized benchtop measurement is shown to demonstrate a possible sensor calibration. For this purpose, an 8-channel parallel transmission pulse generator and 8-channel transmit/receive RF coil were used, which allows to generate numerous different RF field exposures by modifying the amplitudes and phase combination of the transmit channels. External reference E-field probes and fiber-optic temperature sensors are placed close to the electrodes and compared to the measured implant sensor signal (Figure 9).

Figure 8: E-field and temperature rise calibration setup for the implant sensor. More details about the setup and reference probes can be found in the corresponding references.^{1,3}

Figure 9: Implant sensor readings in comparison to the reference E-field and temperature measurements at the electrode for a variety of different RF exposure scenarios. The panel on the left demonstrates that E-field measurements at the reference implant tip versus implant sensor measurements. The limits of the implant sensor as previously discussed are shown for very low induced E-field signals, whereas the external reference E-field probe saturates at higher induced values. Both E-field (left) and temperature (right) readings from external reference probes correspond to the induced implant sensor signal.

Both E-field and temperature measurements from external reference probes can be detected reliably within a measured uncertainty by the implant sensor signal. As already discussed, very low induced E-fields cannot be reliably determined, which needs to be considered. For very high induced E-field values the external E-field reference probe used in these experiments saturated. This is due to the experimental conditions applied in this example and must be avoided in real-life calibrations.

It should be noted that the maximum values of induced E-fields at the electrodes are dependent on the implant electrode model, materials and RF exposure field and frequency, which requires accurate placement of the external reference probes. An example of the SAR distribution around a reference electrode at 128 MHz exposure ($B_0 = 3$ T) and at 298 MHz exposure ($B_0 = 7$ T) are shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11, respectively. Insulated leads have the hot-spot location at their uninsulated lead tip. If temperature is being used for calibration, it must be furthermore considered that the maximum hotspot location might change with time and tissue type. All these effects may be accounted for in the uncertainty budget, e.g. by using EM and thermal simulations⁴ or to determine the location for sensor placement at the electrodes.⁴

Figure 10: Simulation results of (A-D) RF induced E-fields of a reference implant electrode for a 128MHz RF exposure and different background tissue types and (E-H) corresponding thermal simulations at the electrode. (I) Temperature evolution over an RF heating period of 60s at the location marked with 'x'.

Figure 11: Simulation results of (A-D) RF induced E-fields of a reference implant electrode for a 298MHz RF exposure and different background tissue types and (E-H) corresponding thermal simulations at the electrode. (I) Temperature evolution over an RF heating period of 60s at the location marked with 'x'.

In principle, either field based or temperature-based sensors, as exemplified by a thermistor based implant sensor located at the electrode tip (Figure 12), can be used to determine the RF-safety threat accurately.²

Figure 12: RF-induced temperature rise at the implant tip measured with an embedded thermistor. (A) Temperature measurement during application of 64 different RF pulses (0.5s), followed by 0.5s cooling period. (B) A zoomed single temperature rise depicting high resolution temperature measurement is shown.

4.2 Wireless communication between Implant and IIU

The wireless communication between implant electronics and IIU can be implemented using Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), which is widely adopted in AIMDs already. This affects the timing requirements in smart implant concept because BLE is a discrete communication scheme, where the connected devices are mostly disconnected and could sleep to reduce battery consumption. The communication happens at a handshaked connection intervals. In case of the presented reference implant, where RMS E-field readings were transmitted, BLE v5 was implemented. Sensor readings can however also be pre-processed, reduced, compressed etc. so it strongly depends on the implemented sensors (e.g., slower temperature readings versus E-field), electronics or targeted uncertainties, how much data needs to be transmitted and under which timing constrains (e.g. in the case of continuous monitoring). Timing constraints will be furthermore impacted by the chosen connection interval and slave (implant) latency between master (IIU) and slave (7.5 ms and 0, respectively, in the presented reference implant example) and a trigger signal (e.g. to indicate the start of the MR calibration sequence). The processing time of the trigger signal together with the implant programming overhead is a constant latency, which was overall 100-200ms in the proof-of-concept experimental setups.³ For continuous monitoring of the RF-induced heating threat, a sampling rate around ~ 1 Hz should in general be sufficient to prevent excessive temperature rise in tissue surrounding the implant electrode.

In principle electromagnetic interferences generated by the implant and IIU could create MR imaging artefacts, which needs to be tested. If BLE, which operates at 2.4GHz, is used for wireless communication the risk, however, is relatively low, since current clinical MR systems use imaging frequencies <300MHz. In the investigated examples no imaging artefacts have been noticed with BLE operation at a 3T (128MHz) MR scanner.³

The communicated data between the implant and IIU can include further information on the implant and its technical capabilities, e.g. support of multi-channel transmission mode, continuous monitoring etc. Furthermore, since safety relevant information is being transmitted, data consistency checks need to be performed.

4.3 Communication between IIU and MR scanner

In the manual control approach, the IIU is an (external) part of the implant (Figure 1) and communication with the MR scanner is solely performed by the operator. For the automatic control mode (Figure 2), the IIU interface to the MR scanner depends on the MR vendor specific communication interfaces (wireless, wired, or optical fibre) and needs to comply with the before mentioned timing and data consistency requirements.

An example of the communication workflow between an implant, IIU or BLE server and a pTx console of an MR scanner is illustrated in Figure 13.

Figure 13 Example of a communication protocol between an implant, an IIU (BLE server) and a pTx console of an MR scanner.³

5 Methodology

Within a patient-specific MR scan, the following methodology is performed:

1. Implant connection to IIU is established.
2. A low-power MR calibration sequence is run, while the implant operates in MR measurement mode.
3. MR transmission values are adjusted for an implant safe scanning mode based on the measurements by the implant sensor.
4. The actual MR scan is executed applying implant safe MR transmission values. Optional: Continuous monitoring of the implant sensor detects unsafe conditions, e.g. due to patient movement and the scan can be aborted or the RF power adjusted accordingly.

5.1 Implant connection to IIU

The IIU communicates with the MR operator or MR scanner to adjust the implant safe scanning mode. In a first step, the MR operator or MR scanner needs to be informed that an implant is connected and that the implant is equipped with a sensor capable to detect RF implant safety. In general, the communication will be bidirectional since the IIU might need to switch the implant into MR sensing mode. The devices also share device specific properties such as trigger latency.

5.2 Low-power MR calibration

In a low power calibration scan, the induced RF is measured by the implant in a patient-specific scenario considering the actual implant location in the RF coil used for the actual MR scan to be delivered to the patient.

The calibration scan in MR depends on the embedded implant sensor type and the MR transmission mode (single or multi-channel). In single channel transmission only one reference value is needed to relate the input signal of the implant to the actual patient hazard, measured in any suitable hazard metric (see e.g. Figure 9). For the general case of multiple transmission channels, a new option comes into play that is not available from single-channel scanners, the possibility to not just ensure

safe scanning but rather to optimize image quality under the constraint of implant safety. One way to achieve that is to construct the so-called sensor-Q-matrix (\mathbf{Q}_s) as follows:² The implant sensor denoted as X in the smart implant safety concept can be written using the \mathbf{Q}_s as follows:

$$X = \mathbf{u}^H \mathbf{Q}_s \mathbf{u}, \quad (1)$$

Where X is the implant sensor, \vec{u} denotes complex valued RF excitation signal setting in the MRI system and the superscript H denotes the Hermitian adjoint. The rank of \mathbf{Q}_s is determined by the number of independent RF channels (N). For RMS sensors without phase information, N^2 measurements are required to construct \mathbf{Q}_s^X as follows:

$$Q_{S,kl}^X = \begin{cases} (X_{kl} - X_k - X_l) + j(X_{kl}^\dagger - X_k - X_l) & \text{for } k \neq l \text{ and } k < l \\ (X_{kl} - X_k - X_l) - j(X_{kl}^\dagger - X_k - X_l) & \text{for } k \neq l \text{ and } k > l \\ 2X_k & \text{for } k = l \end{cases}, \quad (2)$$

where X_k is the sensor reading when only channel k transmits, X_{kl} denotes the sensor reading when channels k and l transmit simultaneously in phase, and X_{kl}^\dagger the same for a $\pi/2$ phase difference between both channels, while the channels' amplitudes are always identical. The measurands in the matrix can be rectified voltages using a diode or temperatures using a thermistor.

An RF only sequence is required for the calibration scan (\mathbf{Q}_s). The abovementioned RMS sensors average the RF energy; therefore, in principle, any pulse shape could be utilized. Here, a rectangular RF pulse shape is used as the calibration sequence. During the \mathbf{Q}_s acquisition, the transmitted RF pulse length should be greater than the settling time of the implant readout electronics (e.g. 1.2 μ s in Figure 6) and contain a sufficient number of samples to accurately determine the implant tip E-field ($\sim 7.8 \mu$ s for the abovementioned reference implant electronics). As an example, 7.5 ms long RF pulses were transmitted by a 3T MR system showing sensor signals adequately detecting the transmitted RF pulses in various RF excitation modes (Figure 14).

Figure 14: A single measurement for E-field based Q_s calibration. Several transmitted RF pulses are ~ 7.5 ms long and the reference implant can precisely sample the rectangular RF envelope.

In multi-channel transmission, a more advanced MR sequence is required, as described by Equation 2. In addition, sufficient recording memory (e.g., random access memory, RAM) to store the sensor signals might need to be considered.

An example of the 8-channel calibration scan using the reference implant is shown in Figure 15. There, 68 (64 Q_s + 4 timestamp) pulses were transmitted by the MR system and different channel combinations induce unique voltage readings in the implant sensor. A total of 58 ms recording time was used by the implant, while the acquisition window for the Q_s measurements is within 8 ms. The first and last two pulses were placed to detect the start of the pulse stream and utilized for timing and error detection/correction due to BLE connection, where a 7.5 ms connection interval was used. From the MR perspective, the RF sequence properties might need to be adjusted based on the implant information received by the IIU (i.e. RF pulse lengths and amplitudes, number of RF pulses). The Q_s calibration pulses are acquired by the implant and the complex-valued Q_s can be calculated either in the implant or the IIU (see Figure 16).

Figure 15: Example of the acquisition of Q_s calibration signals over 10 consecutive measurements. 68 (64 Q_s , 4 timestamp) distinct calibration pulses acquired in a single RF sequence to determine Q_s are shown. A) Measured Q_s raw data for 10-consecutive 7.5ms long RF transmissions including timing uncertainties of the BLE timing interval of 7.5ms. B) Corrected Q_s acquisitions. The first and last two RF pulses are used as timestamps for the synchronization.³

Figure 16: An example of a calculated Q_s matrix amplitude and phase for an 8-channel RF coil using the reference implant. The Q_s matrix can be used to see how strong RF channels couple to the implant (e.g. channel 4 and 5). This information can be used to calculate transmission modes that suppress RF induced heating and to set safe RF power limits.

5.3 Implant safe scanning and monitoring

Once the Q_s is known after the MR calibration scan, the RF heating threat can be directly calculated for any RF power settings and consequently any MR sequence at the scanner. This information can be used to understand if RF power limits need further restrictions with the presence of the implant and to which degree for safe implant scanning. Through the previously discussed implant sensor calibrations (see chapter 4.1), the RF-induced SAR or temperature increase can be directly predicted from Q_s , while the implant sensor can be utilized as a safety watchdog, monitoring the RF induced threat during an MR scan. This is exemplified in Figure 17.

Figure 17 Prediction of RF-induced heating based on Q_s measurements in a 3T MRI. A two-channel birdcage body coil was used for transmission. A) Temperature rise vs nominal flip angle. B) Temperature rise vs. measured transmitted RF power at the MR scanner. C) Q_s raw data from 4 low-power MR calibration scans D) Predicted vs. measured temperature increase for different RF transmission modes. E) Q_s raw data from a different implant location and F) corresponding temperature increase for different complex excitation vectors compared to Q_s based predictions of the temperature increase.²

Performance boost through multi-channel transmission

If a multi-channel transmission system is available (e.g., most current 3T MR scanners have a 2-channel RF body coil and 7T scanners an 8-channel RF system), the \mathbf{Q}_S information can be furthermore processed to suppress RF-induced heating compared to the conventional imaging mode (e.g. circular polarization, CP). This allows for higher RF power limits, which benefit MR imaging. The calculations of the implant safe scanning mode using pTx suppression can be performed by the MR system, which only needs to know \mathbf{Q}_S from the IIU.

An eigenvalue decomposition of \mathbf{Q}_S is obtained by calculating the eigenvalues (λ) and eigenvectors (\mathbf{v}):

$$\mathbf{Q}_S \mathbf{v} = \lambda \mathbf{v} \quad (4)$$

With this information, a mitigating Orthogonal Projection (OP)¹ vector can be calculated suppressing the RF-induced signals substantially. The OP method is based on an orthogonal projection of a vector used for imaging (CP) to a worst-case (WC) voltage vector \mathbf{u}_{WC} , i.e. the eigenvector with the largest eigenvalue of \mathbf{Q}_S :

$$\mathbf{u}_{OP} = \mathbf{u}_{CP} - \mathbf{u}_{WC}(\mathbf{u}_{WC} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{CP}) \quad (5)$$

The complex vector \mathbf{u}_{OP} , which consists of channel wise amplitude and phase combinations for the implant safe scanning mode, is entirely calculated on-the-fly from \mathbf{Q}_S and no additional imaging experiments are needed. The OP method maintains image quality to a large extent, since the imaging vector \mathbf{u}_{CP} is used as a starting point to compute \mathbf{u}_{OP} (Equation 5, Figure 18). In Figure 19, the patient-specific calibrations using the reference implant with wireless transmission in a 3T MR setting was shown for 6 different realistic deep brain stimulation (DBS) trajectories.³ Using the sensor signal and \mathbf{Q}_S acquisitions, RF-induced heating was substantially suppressed and monitored, without reducing the total transmitted RF power.

Figure 18 Example of 3T MR images of the orthogonal projection (OP) method compared to a conventional imaging mode (B_1 -shim). Both transmission modes use the same average transmitted RF power. The MR signal intensity profile is largely maintained for both transmission settings, even though RF induced heating at the electrode tip is largely suppressed in OP mode. ¹⁻³

Figure 19: Example of six different DBS implant lead trajectories and sensor-based detection and mitigation of RF induced heating inside a 3T MR scanner. (A) Measured Q_s for each DBS lead configuration. (B) Measured implant sensor signals for worst case, circular polarization and orthogonal projection transmission mode for the same transmitted average RF power. (C) Corresponding RF-induced temperature measurements at the implant electrode using external fiber-optic temperature probes. The orthogonal projection successfully suppresses RF-induced heating for all implant configurations without reducing the limits for RF power transmission.

6 Risk assessment

To assess the risks of the smart implant safety concept in the described operational modes a failure modes and effects analysis (FMEA) according to IEC 60812 was performed applying risk assessment techniques according to ISO/IEC 31010.

6.1 FMEA – Smart implant safety mode

Severity (S); Occurrence (O); Detectability (D); Risk Priority Number (RPN);

Severity	consequence	S	Occurrence	O	Prevention	Detectability	D	RPN	Categories
catastrophic	damage of health, regulatory requirements	4	high	4	No preventive action	Testing method does not exist	4	48-64	X – unacceptable
major	loss of a primary function	3	medium	3	Preventive action set up. Verification is missing.	Best practice – modification of design is not available	3	27-36	1 – undesirable
marginal	loss or limitation of a secondary function	2	low	2	Preventive action set up. Verification passed.	Best practice – modification of design is available	2	12-24	2 – acceptable
minor	identification only by an expert	1	remote	1	Failure/cause are eliminated or cannot be present in the design.	Previous testing without defect or cause.	1	1-8	3 - minor

Module	Defect	Consequence	S	Potential causes	O	Prevention	Current control (detection)	D	RPN	Corrective action
Implant	No connection to implant sensor	RF induced heating cannot be detected	3	Faulty connections	1	No smart implant safe scanning mode	Implant status transmitted to IIU	2	6	Internal test routines
Implant	Implant sensor readings outside of specifications	Measurements cannot accurately assess RF-induced heating	3	Faulty electronics/sensors, connections	1	No smart implant safe scanning mode	Send implant status to IIU after internal testing	2	6	Internal test routines
Implant	Implant sensor calibration does not provide realistic temperature increase at implant tip	Higher exposures than anticipated with potential risk to tissue damage	4	Implant sensor calibrations not performed properly	2	Repeat calibration, add risk margin	Testing protocols to investigate RF induced heating with external probes and/or simulations	2	16	Standardized testing to investigate various exposure conditions also under MR exposure (gradients, RF)
Implant	Qs measurements for a large number of transmission channels (Qs>1) cannot be performed	MR calibration scan cannot be performed to assess the full Qs matrix	2	Limitation in implant memory to measure a large Qs	2	Smart implant safe scanning limited to single-channel transmission	Check if implant safe mode compatible with implant and MR system (number of transmission channels)	2	8	Transmit the max number of transmission channels that can be detected by implant to IIU

Implant	Latencies in Qs measurements (Qs>1)	Qs data cannot be reliably associated to specific transmission channels	2	Communication latencies in wireless communication	3	Smart implant safe scanning limited to single-channel transmission	Detect timing pulses (start/end) in Qs transmission protocol	2	12	Synchronize data according to timing pulses, perform consistency check
Implant Interface Unit	Communication with implant not possible	Sensor information cannot be transmitted to IIU and implant safe scanning mode cannot be started	3	EMI disturbances, low-signal amplitudes	2	No smart implant safe scanning mode	Communication protocol unsuccessful	2	12	Display that implant safe scanning mode not feasible, retry connection IIU <-> implant
Implant Interface Unit	Received implant information corrupted/wrong	Wrong RF induced heating threat estimated based on the calibration file	4	Data transmission errors	1	Abort MR scan	Checksum control after every transmission	2	8	Send error message if data transmission corrupted
Implant Interface Unit	Large communication latencies with Implant (continuous monitoring)	Delay in assessing RF induced heating	4	Large datasets, wireless communication latencies	2	Abort MR scan	Detect changes to previous time points measured	2	16	Send error message if latencies above critical value

Implant Interface Unit	Communication with MR scanner not possible (automatic mode)	Implant safe scanning mode cannot be enabled	3	Loose cables, communication issues between IIU and MR system	2	No smart implant safe scanning mode	Test handshake protocol/checksum	2	12	Send error message that smart implant scanning not feasible
Implant Interface Unit	Latency in displaying current RF-induced safety parameters (continuous monitoring, manual mode)	Critical safety parameters are displayed too late for the MR operator to abort the MR scan (e.g. in case of patient movement)	4	Errors in display update	2	Abort MR scan	Device testing under MR conditions	2	16	Add a moving icon indicating continuous monitoring mode to guarantee that display functionality works
Implant Interface Unit	Latency in transmitting RF-induced safety parameters (continuous monitoring) to MR scanner (automatic mode)	Critical safety parameters are transmitted too late, risk of exceeded RF-induced tissue heating	4	Communication latencies outside specifications	2	Abort MR scan	Test communication latencies	2	16	Implement handshake dataset to track communication latencies

MR Operator	MR calibration scan did not work	Qs detection not enabled and no sensor measurements performed	3	MR calibration scan not started at IIU	2	No smart implant safe scanning mode, repeat procedure	Display at IIU that MR calibration not performed yet	2	12	Display at IIU that MR calibration scan can be started and display if successful
MR Operator	Implant safe mode incorrectly set (manual mode)	Potential for elevated tissue temperatures/fields	4	Wrong implant safe parameters entered from IIU to MR system	2	No smart implant safe scanning mode, repeat procedure	Display of RF induced values after implant safe mode setting	2	16	Reference sensor measurements before and after implant safe mode transmission, Continuous monitoring of RF-induced sensor signal, redo calibration

MR Scanner	MR calibration scan did not work	Implant safe mode cannot be applied	3	Communication between IIU and MR scanner or IIU and implant did not work	2	No smart implant safe scanning mode, repeat procedure	Testing of communication	2	12	Fall back to restricted RF power output mode, check communication and retry
MR Scanner	Implant safe mode does not suppress RF induced heating (continuous monitoring)	Elevated tissue temperatures during MR sequence	4	Patient movement, Change of patient position by MR operator	3	Abort MR scan	Continuous monitoring of implant sensor measurements by IIU	2	24	Display warning and abort scan, ask operator to redo the MR calibration scan, Add a regular MR calibration scan within MR scanning protocols

7 References

1. Winter L, Silemek B, Petzold J, et al. Parallel transmission medical implant safety testbed: Real-time mitigation of RF induced tip heating using time-domain E-field sensors. *Magn Reson Med*. 2020;84(6):3468-3484. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.28379>
2. Silemek B, Seifert F, Petzold J, et al. Rapid safety assessment and mitigation of radiofrequency induced implant heating using small root mean square sensors and the sensor matrix Qs. *Magn Reson Med*. 2022;87(1):509-527. doi:10.1002/mrm.28968
3. Silemek B, Seifert F, Petzold J, Brühl R, Ittermann B, Winter L. Wirelessly interfacing sensor-equipped implants and MR scanners for improved safety and imaging. *Magn Reson Med*. 2023;90(6):2608-2626. doi:10.1002/mrm.29818
4. Petzold J, Schmitter S, Silemek B, et al. Towards an integrated RF safety concept for implant carriers in MRI based on sensor-equipped implants and parallel transmission. *NMR Biomed*. 2023;36(7):e4900. doi:10.1002/nbm.4900
5. International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). Medical electrical equipment. Particular requirements for the safety of magnetic resonance equipment for medical diagnosis. *Int Stand IEC60601-2-33*. 2002. <https://cir.nii.ac.jp/crid/1573387449839698048>. Accessed March 31, 2025.
6. Silemek B, Açikel V, Atalar E. RF safety of active implantable medical devices. *eMagRes*. 2019;8(2):103-120. doi:10.1002/9780470034590.emrstm1587
7. Winter L, Seifert F, Zilberti L, Murbach M, Ittermann B. MRI-Related Heating of Implants and Devices: A Review. *J Magn Reson Imaging*. 2021;53(6):1646-1665. doi:10.1002/jmri.27194
8. ISO-TS 10974:2018 S. *Assessment of the Safety of Magnetic Resonance Imaging for Patients with an Active Implantable Medical Device*. Geneva, Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization; 2018.
9. Henderson JM, Tkach J, Phillips M, Baker K, Shellock FG, Rezai AR. Permanent neurological deficit related to magnetic resonance imaging in a patient with implanted deep brain stimulation electrodes for Parkinson's disease: case report. *Neurosurgery*. 2005;57(5):E1063; discussion E1063.
10. Boutet A, Chow CT, Narang K, et al. Improving Safety of MRI in Patients with Deep Brain Stimulation Devices. *Radiology*. 2020;296(2):250-262. doi:10.1148/radiol.2020192291
11. Shetty AS, Ludwig DR, Andrews TJ. Invited Commentary: MRI in Patients with Active Implanted Medical Devices: Demand Will Only Grow. *RadioGraphics*. 2024;44(3):e230231. doi:10.1148/rg.230231

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12. Pitman BM, Ariyaratnam J, Williams K, et al. The Burden of Cardiac Implantable Electronic Device Checks in the Peri-MRI Setting: The CHECK-MRI Study. *Heart Lung Circ.* 2023;32(2):252-260. doi:10.1016/j.hlc.2022.10.005
 13. Celentano E, Caccavo V, Santamaria M, et al. Access to magnetic resonance imaging of patients with magnetic resonance-conditional pacemaker and implantable cardioverter-defibrillator systems: results from the Really ProMRI study. *EP Eur.* 2018;20(6):1001-1009. doi:10.1093/europace/eux118
 14. Falowski S, Safriel Y, Ryan MP, Hargens L. The Rate of Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Patients with Deep Brain Stimulation. *Stereotact Funct Neurosurg.* 2016;94(3):147-153. doi:10.1159/000444760
 15. Silemek B, Yalaz M, Seifert F, et al. Built-in RF safety for active implants: Harnessing impedance measurements from a commercial deep brain stimulator. In: *Proc. Intl. Soc. Mag. Reson. Med.* Vol 32. Singapore; 2024:0786.
 16. Silemek B, Seifert F, Brühl R, Ittermann B, Winter L. Impedance measurements detect the temperature rise near DBS. In: *Proc. Intl. Soc. Mag. Reson. Med.* Vol 33. Hawai'i, United States; 2025:0179.
 17. Silemek B, Acikel V, Oto C, et al. A temperature sensor implant for active implantable medical devices for in vivo subacute heating tests under MRI. *Magn Reson Med.* 2018;79(5):2824-2832. doi:10.1002/mrm.26914
 18. Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB). Wireless Reference Implant. Open Source Imaging. <https://www.opensourceimaging.org/project/wireless-reference-implant/>. Published 2023. Accessed March 27, 2025.
 19. ASTM F2182 - 11. ASTM F2182 - 11 Standard Test Method for Measurement of Radio Frequency Induced Heating Near Passive Implants During Magnetic Resonance Imaging. <https://www.astm.org/DATABASE.CART/HISTORICAL/F2182-11.htm>. Accessed March 22, 2020.